

Ancient DNA Service Report: Estimation of Genetic Sex

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Date prepared: February 4th 2020

Number of samples: 16

Service provided: aDNA extraction and NGS sequencing for screening purposes.

BACKGROUND

16 samples were sent to the ancient DNA lab at the University of Tartu for DNA analysis in fall 2019. All were sampled and processed (see Methods), 15 yielded sequenceable DNA libraries and these were shotgun sequence screened at the University of Tartu Institute of Genomics Core Facility.

QUALITATIVE RESULTS

Results are summarised in Table 1. Average endogenous human content is 3.9% with 3 samples over 10%. The average genomic coverage obtained per sample is 0.017 with 0 samples over 0.1X and thus of sufficient coverage for kinship analysis. The average contamination rate is 0.51% (mtDNA) and all samples were less than 2%, well within the generally acceptable range (up to 5%).

All samples exhibit fragment length (average 41 base pairs) and damage patterns consistent with authentic ancient DNA (figs. 2 - 31). The average percentage of C > T transitions in the terminal ends are on average 20% (10% min to >30% max).

GENETIC SEX ESTIMATION RESULTS

The genetic sex of all samples was able to be estimated (table 1, fig. 1). Two samples, CAS005 and CAS010 were not able to be assigned due to low coverage leading to high standard errors (not enough reads to get a meaningful result). Two, CAS009 and CAS013 were “consistent with XY but not XX” meaning that these samples had a low number of reads, thus the standard errors are high, but it is most likely that these individuals were biologically male. One sample, CAS015 was “consistent with XX but not XY” meaning that this samples had a low number of reads, thus the standard errors are high, but it is most likely that these individuals were biologically female. It might be noted that CAS0015, CAS006 and CAS013 have a similar number of total reads mapping to the X and Y chromosomal references. CAS006 is clearly female and CAS013 has a much higher R_y value consistent with a male sample. Since CAS015 is a bit of an outlier in this respect, it is also possible that CAS0015 is male, or could possibly be XXY. Additional sequencing would be needed to determine the actual result. Nine samples were definitively estimated as XX (female, n=7) or XY (male, n=2) with very low standard errors (fig. 1).

Figure 1 Ratio of reads mapping to the Y chromosome vs. total sex chromosomes. Standard errors are in red. Ry value of 0.08 indicates the cut-off for male samples.

DETAILED METHODS

Sampling, decontamination and extraction

Inside a class IIB hood in the dedicated aDNA facility of the University of Tartu Institute of Genomics, root portions of teeth and sections of bone were removed with a sterile drill wheel. Root and bone portions were briefly brushed to remove surface dirt, any varnish or lacquer, and microbial film with full strength household bleach (6% w/v NaOCl) using a disposable toothbrush that was soaked in 6% (w/v) bleach prior to use. They were then soaked in 6% (w/v) bleach for 5 minutes. Samples were rinsed twice with 18.2 MΩcm H₂O and soaked in 70% (v/v) Ethanol for 2 minutes, transferred to a clean paper towel on a rack inside a class IIB hood with the UV light on and allowed to dry. They were weighed and transferred to PCR-clean 5 ml or 15 ml conical tubes (Eppendorf) for chemical extraction.

Inside a class IIB hood, per 100 mg of each sample, 2 ml of 0.5M EDTA Buffer pH 8.0 (Fluka) and 50 µl of Proteinase K 10 mg/ml (Roche) was added. Tubes were rocked in an incubator for 72 hours at room temperature. Extracts were concentrated to 250 µl using Amplicon Ultra-15 concentrators with a 30 kDa filter (Millipore).

Samples were purified according to manufacturer's instructions using buffers from the Minelute™ PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen) with the following changes: 1) the use of High-Volume spin columns (Roche); 2) 10X PB buffer instead of 5X; and 3) samples incubated with EB buffer (Qiagen) at 37C for 10 minutes prior to elution. The columns were transferred to clean, labelled, 1.5ml Eppendorf tubes. One hundred microlitres EB buffer is added to the membrane and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for two minutes after the 10-minute incubation and

stored at -20 C. Only one extraction was performed per sample for screening and 30µl used for libraries.

Library amplification

Some sample extracts may have been treated for inhibitor removal prior to library building with the OneStep PCR Inhibitor Removal Kit (D6030, Zymo Research) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Library preparation was conducted using a protocol modified from the manufacturer's instructions included in the NEBNext® Library Preparation Kit for 454 (E6070S, New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA) as detailed in (Meyer & Kircher 2010). DNA was not fragmented and reactions were scaled to half volume, adaptors were made as described in (Meyer & Kircher, 2010) and used in a final concentration of 2.5µM each. DNA was purified on MinElute columns (Qiagen). Libraries were amplified using the following PCR set up: 50µl DNA library, 1X PCR buffer, 2.5mM MgCl₂, 1 mg/ml BSA, 0.2µM inPE1.0, 0.2mM dNTP each, 0.1U/µl HGS Taq Diamond and 0.2µM indexing primer. Cycling conditions were: 5' at 94C, followed by 18 cycles of 30 seconds each at 94C, 60C, and 68C, with a final extension of 7 minutes at 72C. Amplified products were purified using MinElute columns and eluted in 35 µl EB (Qiagen). Three verification steps were implemented to make sure library preparation was successful and to measure the concentration of dsDNA/sequencing libraries – fluorometric quantitation (Qubit, Thermo Fisher Scientific), parallel capillary electrophoresis (Fragment Analyser, Advanced Analytical) and qPCR.

Mapping and Genotyping

The samples were shotgun-sequenced on the Illumina NextSeq500/550 using the High-Output single-end 75 base pair kit. Before mapping, the sequences of adaptors and indexes and poly-G tails occurring due to the specifics of the NextSeq500/550 technology were removed from the ends of DNA sequences using cutadapt 1.9 (Martin, 2011). Sequences shorter than 30 bp were also removed with the same program to avoid random mapping of sequences from other species.

The sequence reads were mapped to reference sequence GRCh37 (hg19) using Burrows-Wheeler Aligner (BWA 0.7.12) (Li & Durbin, 2009) command `aln` with seeding disabled. After mapping, the sequences were converted to BAM format and only sequences that mapped to the human genome were kept with samtools 1.9 (Li et al., 2009). Next, multiple bam files from the same individual, but different runs were merged using samtools merge, reads with mapping quality under 30 were filtered out and duplicates were removed with picard 2.12 (<http://broadinstitute.github.io/picard/index.html>).

aDNA Authentication

As a result of degradation over time, aDNA can be distinguished from modern DNA by certain characteristics: short fragments and a high frequency of C > T substitutions at the 5' ends of sequences due to cytosine deamination. The program mapDamage2.0 (Jónsson et al., 2013) was used to estimate the frequency of 5' C > T transitions.

mtDNA contamination was estimated using the method from (Scheib et al. 2018), which aligns the raw mtDNA reads to the RSRS (Behar et al. 2012), determines the haplotype using GATK pileup (McKenna et al., 2010) counts the number of heterozygous reads on haplotype-

defining sites as well as adjacent sites and calculates a ratio that takes into account ancient DNA damage by excluding positions where a major allele is C or G and the minor is T or A respectively.

X chromosome based contamination estimate is calculated using ANGSD on male samples with $>0.1X$ autosomal average genomic coverage as described in (Rasmussen et al., 2011).

Calculating general statistics, determining genetic sex

Samtools-1.9 (Li et al., 2009) option stats was used to determine the number of final reads, average read length, average coverage etc.

Genetic sex was calculated using the script sexing.py from (Skoglund et al., 2013), estimating the fraction of reads with mapping quality > 30 mapping to Y chromosome out of all reads mapping to either X or Y chromosome. Genetic sexing confirmed morphological sex estimates.

Table 1 Assignment of genetic sex.

Lab ID	Structure	Individual	Site	NchrY	Ry	SE	95% CI Min	95% CI Max	Assignment
CAS003	UE 12730	12737 Ind. 5	Los Melgarejos	1,017	0.0043	0.0001	0.0041	0.0046	XX
CAS007	UE 10220	10223 Ind. 7	Los Melgarejos	1,076	0.0045	0.0001	0.0042	0.0048	XX
CAS001	UE 10910	10912 Ind. 1	Los Melgarejos	7617	0.0838	0.0009	0.0820	0.0856	XY
CAS011	UE 12390	12392	Los Melgarejos	3028	0.0831	0.0014	0.0803	0.0860	XY
CAS002	UE 10910	10912 Ind. 2	Los Melgarejos	183	0.0054	0.0004	0.0046	0.0062	XX
CAS004	UE 410	412 Ind. 1	Los Melgarejos	38	0.0035	0.0006	0.0024	0.0046	XX
CAS012	UE 2190	2192	Los Melgarejos	43	0.0034	0.0005	0.0024	0.0044	XX
CAS008	UE 12730	12733 Ind. 1	Los Melgarejos	38	0.0053	0.0009	0.0036	0.0070	XX
CAS009	UE 12730	12734 Ind. 2	Los Melgarejos	136	0.0737	0.0061	0.0618	0.0856	consistent with XY but not XX
CAS015	UE 10910	10912 Ind. 3	Los Melgarejos	11	0.0335	0.0099	0.0141	0.0530	consistent with XX but not XY
CAS006	UE 10220	10223 Ind. 8	Los Melgarejos	1	0.0018	0.0018	-0.0018	0.0054	XX
CAS013	UE 3300	3303	Los Melgarejos	16	0.0541	0.0131	0.0283	0.0798	consistent with XY but not XX
CAS010	UE 12370	12738 Ind. 6	Los Melgarejos	6	0.0508	0.0202	0.0112	0.0905	Not Assigned
CAS005	UE 410	412 Ind. 5	Los Melgarejos	2	0.0625	0.0428	-0.0214	0.1464	Not Assigned

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